

FREQUENCY AND PREVALENCE OF DIABETES MELLITUS IN PREGNANT WOMEN OF QUETTA DISTRICT, BALOCHISTAN, PAKISTAN.

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ABSTRACT

GDM as the main topic of this study which represents a survey conducted among pregnant mothers in Quetta city of Balochistan province that consequently shows whether diabetes mellitus (DM) is occurring frequently and prevalent in pregnant women or not. During the time period of January 2023 to September 2023, 564 pregnant women who were enrolled from Sheikh Khalifah Bin Zayyad Hospital, Sandeman Provisional Hospital, and Bolan Medical Complex Hospital in Quetta took part in a cross-sectional study. Demographic information, present clinical examinations and laboratory tests with, for example, the Oral Glucose Tolerance Test (OGTT), level of Glycated Hemoglobin (HbA1c), and Fasting Plasma Glucose (FPG) that were used in the stage of information collection. Digging deeper into the case of Quetta District, we had a shocking revelation that the phenomenon of GDM among pregnant women there had reached a high level; when the data was broken down and analyzed ethnically, a variation on the prevalence rates was emerged. The most regular occurrence of 30 is the one. 3.5%, Baluchi women of the second with 14.4% percent. 04%. This is a result of increased maternal age, BMI before the pregnancy, family history of diabetes, ethnicity, GDM before, and multiple pregnancies showing the affected factors in GDM sustainability. The study ends by pointing out the alarming that the GDM among expecting mothers in Quetta District is very common and this is a public health issue that needs to be addressed. The research highlighted the fundamental steps for health providers and policy makers to design specific programs, in the area, which would allow early detection, management, treatment and prevention of GDM by focusing on the important risk factors and consequences linked to the disease.

1. INTRODUCTION.

Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), regarded as diabetes mellitus (DM) in pregnant women, is a serious issue that always carries the health risk for both the mother and the fetus (Johns et al., 2018). Increased blood glucose level is a result of the body's inability to manufacture or use insulin effectively during pregnancy, hence this is the disease. In the opinion of Karasneh et al. (2021), the GDM pregnancy has several risks, including macrosomia, hypoglycemia in the kid, and a higher chance of cesarean to the mother. The noxious impact of the Diabetes Mellitus (DM) on mothers' health is a grave issue that threatens not only them but also their unborn babies. It is very important to know how frequently it occurs and in which communities in order to develop the actions that will be focused on this problem and, thereby, to improve the pregnancy outcomes. In this context, the incidence of GDM is rapidly growing around the globe. Therefore, a much wider knowledge of its risk factors, early detection, and the available effective management tools is urgently needed.

In respect of the diagnostic criteria outlined for gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) based on the International Association of Diabetes and Pregnancy Study Groups (IADPSG), GDM is predicted to afflict 14% of all pregnant women worldwide (Wang et al., 2021). With these numbers which are alarmingly high families are likely to continue living in debt conditions. The authors report that this gives an estimate of 15% of women in the world getting Type 2 Diabetes during their pregnancy. The Middle East and North Africa (MENA) and Southeast Asia (SEA) are the regions with the highest prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), which stand at around 20% and 27%. Oceania and Africa (OC and AFR) have a higher prevalence at 9%, followed by South Asia (SAS) at 8%, whereas the NAC and European regions have the lowest prevalence at approximately 7% (Offomiyor & Rehal 2023). Study specific reports about the GDM rate in Pakistan have varied in approach, however, most sources would agree that the numbers are very high. The estimate fluctuates between 6 to a higher number. 25% to 36. 8%. This means that the figure is somewhere between 1 in 16 and 1 in 3 pregnant women in Pakistan who are affected by GDM (Fatima et al., 2017).

GDM is understood as glucose intolerance which is detected in a person for the first time during pregnancy as informed by Desoye et al, (2007). Motherhood related obesity and the insulin-resistance effect caused by placental hormones are currently thought to be the prime reason for insufficient secretion of insulin and/or the arising of insulin resistance which is just like gestational diabetes as per its nature but the mechanism remains poorly known. Human Placental Lactogen (HPL), prolactin, and placental growth hormones have

been shown to be responsible for the development of gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) through the increase of maternal food intake, mobilization of maternal resources for fetal growth, and elevation of insulin resistance to maternal nutrition (Rassie et al., 2022).

Besides the complexity of genetic, lifestyle and ecological factors in the conception of this phenomenon, in which GDM occur very frequently, risk is also a major public health concern because the disease is extremely dangerous. Besides the fact that gestational diabetes exposes serious health problems for women during their pregnancy, it also leads to the development of many long-term diseases among a mother and her child. Riaz et al. (2019) assert that women with GDM are becoming an ideal candidate group for primary diabetes prevention as they have a higher likelihood of developing T2DM in the future. GDM is known by some to be a mere step off from the onset of Type 2 diabetes which is described as inadequate 3-year dysfunction of pancreatic beta cells.

An Australian study found that Asian women had a higher risk of GDM (11.5% vs. 3.7%), in comparison to Australian women. According to the Kavya (2022), South Asia has a noticeably high prevalence of GDM. There have been reports of frequency variations in Bangladesh ranging from 13.2% to over 40%. There have been reports of a prevalence from Tamil Nadu, India, ranging from 9.9% to 17.8%. Overweight/obesity, a westernized diet and micronutrient deficiencies, advanced maternal age, and a family history of insulin resistance and/or diabetes are risk factors, according to a survey. Even though gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) typically goes away after birth, it can have long-term health effects. These effects include a mother's higher risk of type 2 diabetes (T2DM) and cardiovascular disease (CVD), as well as the child's future risk of obesity, CVD, T2DM, and/or GDM (Plows et al., 2018).

Over 20 million women reported with abnormalities of carbohydrate metabolism in 2019, with about 80% of those cases being GDM, according to the 2019 report published by the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) (Mustad et al., 2020). GDM affects around 1 in 6 pregnancies. GDM was most common in South-East Asia (24%), whereas it was least common in Africa (10%). Nearly 90% of pregnancy-related occurrences of hyperglycemia happened in low- and middle-income nations. The prevalence of GDM varies even within nations based on socioeconomic level and race/ethnicity (Gică & Huluiță 2023).

1. Research Methodology

1.1. Research Design

In order to determine the frequency and prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) in pregnant women reported at various hospitals in the Quetta district, including Sandeman

Provisional Hospital, Bolan Medical Complex Hospital, and Sheikh Khalifah Bin Zayyad Hospital, a cross-sectional study was carried out. There were 564 patients with gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) in total. The study was carried out in accordance with the requirements from January 2023 to September 2023. Several questions served as the foundation for the questionnaire's construction.

1.2. Collection of Blood Samples

1.2.1. Fasting Plasma Glucose (FPG):

To analyze that if a person's blood glucose level is high or not, a 2-3 ml blood sample of him/her is taken when he/she has fasted for 8-12 hours for the Fasting Plasma Glucose (FPG) test. This is the method that is usually carried out in the morning, which estimates the body's ability to manage blood sugar when there has been no recent food intake. In order to get an accurate test for glucose, patients have to stay absolutely fasting during this fasting time period. The health professional picks a vein in the arm using a needle and syringe, then they draw blood from there. The extracted sample is then tested in the laboratory using different methods, such as spectrophotometry or enzymatic tests, to measure the concentration of plasma glucose in it. This method serves as an early detection and reassessment strategy for prediabetes and diabetes mellitus patients, resulting in proper management. In the common understanding pregnancy is accompanied by the FPG (fasting plasma glucose) the pre-pregnancy level. The range of FPG (fasting plasma glucose) is typically less than 92 mg/dL. The Oral Glucose Tolerance Test (OGTT) should be used to additionally test for impaired fasting glucose (IFG), which is defined as an FPG level of 92–125 mg/dL. The most definitive diagnosis of GDM is made when a first and second independent reading of a fasting plasma glucose level is 126 mg/dL or more.

1.2.2. Oral Glucose Tolerance Test (OGTT):

Glucose metabolism is understood with Oral Glucose Tolerance Test (OGTT) which is a test conducted towards the completion of 2 hour oral dose of glucose. A sample of fasting blood is taken after an 8-hour fast. Following that, the patients ingest a glucose solution (usually 75 grams). Blood samples are used to measure glucose levels one and two hours after intake. OGTT is used to diagnose gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) in pregnant patients between weeks 24 and 28. The patient consumes a glucose solution, and blood is drawn to measure glucose metabolism at fasting, one-, and two-hour intervals. Increased readings signify GDM. Healthcare practitioners use institutional and regional recommendations for glucose concentrations and diagnostic criteria when administering and interpreting the test.

1.2.3. Glycated Hemoglobin Test (HbA1c):

There is no need to fast for the Glycated Hemoglobin (HbA1c) test. To calculate the percentage of hemoglobin with linked glucose, which represents average blood sugar levels over a two- to three-month period, a blood sample is obtained. During pregnancy, the Oral Glucose Tolerance Test (OGTT) is the preferred diagnostic approach for patients with Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM); HbA1c testing is not the primary procedure. Although HbA1c is not the major emphasis for GDM, it is still useful for tracking long-term glycemic control in other types of diabetes. Less than 5.7% is considered normal, and 5.7% to 6.4% is considered prediabetes. Two fasting readings > 92 mg/dL or a HbA1c result of 6.5% or higher are required for Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM).

1.3. Inclusion criteria

The current study was deemed appropriate for patients with Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM) who were willing to participate and who fell within the age bracket of solely pregnant patients. Initially, the study's objectives and procedures were explained to the patients, and only those who gave written, informed consent were added to the study. Patients were restricted to one gender (females).

1.4. Exclusion criteria

Participants with any other kind of diabetes mellitus or those with other metabolic conditions were not allowed to participate in the trial.

1.5. Statistical Analysis

The information (gender, etiology, and subclinical characteristics) was gathered into Microsoft Excel sheets. Age distribution, risk variables, clinical forms, and demographic parameters were all shown as percentages. Using the chi-square test and a Mantel–Haenszel analysis (univariate) in the contingency table that made use of Epi-info TM (version 7.3.2.1), the questionnaire-based data, GDM, and prevalence were assessed. With the help of GraphPad Prism (Version 6), graphs were created. When a difference was $P < 0.05$, it was deemed significant.

2. Results

During the final nine months of the trial period, specific examinations were conducted on the patients, leading to the diagnosis of GDM.

Table 1: Factors Influencing GDM Prevalence

Factor	Increased Prevalence	Decreased Prevalence
Mother's Age (above 30)	Yes	No
BMI prior to pregnancy	Yes	No

Diabetes in the Family History	Yes	No
Ethnicity	Asian, Hispanic	Non-Hispanic
Previous GDM	Yes	No
Several Pregnancies	Yes	No

Table 1 illustrates how a number of factors affect the prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) in expectant mothers. Older age, higher BMI prior to pregnancy, family history of diabetes, Asian or Hispanic ancestry, history of GDM, and repeated pregnancies are all linked to higher risks. On the other hand, the risk of GDM is reduced by younger age, lower BMI, lack of family history, non-Hispanic ethnicity, and fewer pregnancies.

Table 2: Possible Diabetes Mellitus Complications During Pregnancy

Condition	Maternal Complications	Fetal Complications
Macrosomia	Preeclampsia, Cesarean section	Large birthweight, birth injuries
Polyhydramnios	Increased amniotic fluid	Respiratory distress, premature birth
Gestational Hypertension	Increased blood pressure	Preeclampsia, IUGR
Hyperglycemia	Diabetic ketoacidosis	Macrosomia, congenital malformations

Table 2 lists the issues that gestational diabetes can cause in mothers and kids, including Macrosomia: large birthweight, cesarean section, preeclampsia, birth trauma, Polyhydramnios is elevated amniotic fluid, dyspnea, preterm birth, IUGR, preeclampsia, elevated blood pressure, and gestational hypertension Hyperglycemia: congenital defects, macrosomia, and diabetic ketoacidosis.

Table 3: Pregnancy-related Diabetes Mellitus Prevalence based on Ethnicity

Ethnic Group	Number of Women Screened	Number of Diabetes Cases	Prevalence (%)
Pashtun	544	164	30.147%
Baloch	530	138	26.037%
Hazara	295	30	10.169%
Others	700	232	33.142%

Figure 1: Pregnancy-related Diabetes Mellitus Prevalence based on Ethnicity

In the ethnic-specific analysis of diabetes mellitus prevalence among pregnant women, Pashtun women had the greatest prevalence (30.15%), with 164 cases out of 544 examined. This is shown in Table 3 and Figure 1. Baloch women constituted 138 cases out of 530 tested, with a frequency of 26.04%. The prevalence among Hazara women was lower, at 10.17%, with 30 cases out of 295 people screened. With 232 cases out of 700 tested, the "Others" group had the highest prevalence, at 33.14%. These results show notable differences in the prevalence of diabetes across various ethnic groups, highlighting the significance of focused interventions and community-specific awareness campaigns for positive outcomes related to maternal health.

Table 4: Impact of Diabetes on Birth Outcomes

Outcome	Number of Cases	Percentage %
Birth weight below 2.5 kg	70	12.4%
Normal Birth Weight (2.5-4 kg)	299	53%
High Birth Weight (>4 kg)	80	14.2%
Neonatal Hypoglycemia	60	10.6%
Birth Defects	55	9.8%

Figure 2: Impact of Diabetes on Birth Outcomes

Table 4 and Graph 2 indicate that more than one in five babies, or 12.4% of all babies born, had birth weights that were significantly below average for the world (70 instances). Although 53% of the cases (299) fell within the healthy normal range, a noteworthy 14.2% of the cases (80) had possibly dangerously high birth weights. The concern was heightened by the fact that 9.8% (55 instances) of babies had birth abnormalities and 10.6% (60 cases) of neonates experienced problems with neonatal hypoglycemia, underscoring the potentially

dangerous effects of gestational diabetes on both mothers and their offspring. Based on a sample of 564 patients, these results emphasize the vital significance of careful observation of neonates born to women with gestational diabetes and complete diabetes control during pregnancy.

Table 5: The status of gestational diabetes mellitus by trimester

Trimester	Number of Patients
First	122
Second	238
Third	204
Total	564

Figure 3: The status of gestational diabetes mellitus by trimester

Table 5 and Figure 3 showed that the second trimester accounted for 42% of all diagnoses of gestational diabetes, with the third trimester accounting for 36% and the first trimester accounting for 22%. This implies that during weeks 24-28, when the usual glucose tolerance test is conducted, a higher number of women have GDM.

Table 6: Age Distribution of Patients with Gestational Diabetes Mellitus

Age Group (years)	Number of Patients
Below 20	13
20-25	97
26-30	203
31-35	181
36 and above	70

Figure 4: Age Distribution of Patients with Gestational Diabetes Mellitus

Table 6 and Figure 4 demonstrate that the age distribution of patients with gestational diabetes is skewed toward the late 20s and early 30s, with the 26–30 age group having the highest prevalence (36%). Following that, the number of patients steadily declines in both the younger and older age categories; just 13 people diagnosed below the age of 20 and 70 over the age of 36. It's interesting to note that a sizeable percentage (17%) of diagnosed cases still belong to the 20–25 age bracket. According to this finding, women in their late 20s and early 30s may benefit from targeted GDM screening and prevention actions.

3. Discussion

In Pakistan, the management of diabetes mellitus (DM) is a major public health issue that does not spare particular age groups and among them pregnant women constitute a crucial concern. In the aging world, dementia is on the rise. The district of Quetta in the province of Balochistan, Balochistan, has specific economic and social and environmental factors that can influence the frequency and prevalence of diabetes mellitus in pregnant women. The body of the research will be the subject matter of this talk: the most decisive findings, the suspected concomitants, and the points for future investigation will be put in the focus.

The research examined the incidence and frequency of Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM) among the pregnant women in the feudal the district of Quetta Balochistan, while helping to understand an integral factor of maternal health. The gestational diabetes is a huge risk to the mothers and babies, which makes its prevalence a major public health issue.

Globally, the frequency of GDM has been on the rise, endeavoring to follow the footsteps of other areas in the world, which have demonstrated the same pattern. The report's results that state that the percentages of GDM for pregnant women belong to the same category as those from around the world, underscore this worldwide trend. This is the reason

why the links between factors like mother age, pre-pregnancy BMI, family history of diabetes and specific ethnicities with the incidence of GDM are so complex and one factor may not entirely explain all the individuals that have this illness.

Research results showed that chances for GDM among these three groups remain different because majority from Pashtun and Baloch ethnic groups demonstrated higher frequencies, compared with ladies from Hazara ethnic group. The burden of GDM is high—this means that the burden has social and cultural significance. That is why it is important to take account of the socio-cultural aspects when looking for better solutions to the problem in the community. The way to improve the maternal health outcomes is the implementation of the targeted interventions and awareness campaigns that are made in accordance with the needs of different ethnic groups.

A type of diabetes, called gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), which is the diabetes that is exclusive to pregnancy, increased by 8% compared to the previous period. Also, 4% was diagnosed with type 2 diabetes in 2021 during the cross-sectional study at the Bolan Medical Complex Hospital, as can be seen in (Munir et al., 2022). Nevertheless, the far higher frequency of 35 was. And it was documented that 8.0% was found in a different investigation done in Combined Military Hospital in 2017. The following inequalities could be cited due to differences in the specific peculiarities of the selected population in Quetta, applied diagnostic criteria, and sampling methodologies.

A higher risk of gestational diabetes mellitus is correlated with an older pregnancy, according to Li et al., 2020. According to a 2017 Combined Military Hospital study, women over 30 had the highest rate of GDM. In the USA, research indicated that the population-attributable fraction was 46.2% overall. This means that if the women had maintained a normal BMI before to becoming pregnant, nearly half of the GDM incidents could have been prevented. Numerous investigations have demonstrated a clear link between obesity and the onset of GDM (Weller 2023).

Older pregnancy is associated with a higher risk of gestational diabetes mellitus, as Li et al. (2020) concluded. Based on the research conducted by a 2017 CIUH, the GDM incidence was the highest in women over 30. In USA, the size of a population-attributable fraction was given as 46 percent. 2% overall. This is to say that if the women had kept a normal BMI before they got pregnant, approximately half of GDM incidents would have been avoided. Countless investigations have proved that there is a clear correlation between obesity and the emergence of GDM (Weller, 2023, p. 8).

In terms of the World Health Organization (WHO) research, the eighth most common cause of death in 2016 was diabetes and in the coming 2030 this disease is expected

to rank third in the list of deadly diseases worldwide, with diabetes being one of the main emerging health problems nowadays (Badakhsh et al., 2019). The aim of this study was to find out how prevalent GDM is in the Middle East. There were in total 33 studies finished between year 2000 and year 2018 with a total of 887,166 participants who used exercise during the end of the study. The East Med region hosts at least eleven of the twenty most frequently occurring air pollutants. The prevalence of GDM was 7%, which is similar to the studies done in Asia earlier (11). 25.6 % and the Eastern Mediterranean account for 12.9 % respectively. This similarity maybe that several of the countries which were reviewed had very similar characteristics among their population.

Pregnancy has a huge match with diabetes mellitus, according to Linden et al. (2022), which is a disease that one has high blood sugar levels. The detection of this gestational condition by mammary gland focal asymmetry among pregnant women all over the world is crucial, for it can influence the health of both mothers and their babies. Let us treat the problem carefully; in order to help its solution.

According to the latest national and international data as well as the reports of the district of Quetta, GDM is the major blood sugar problem encountered in Quetta. Studies have repeatedly proved that the incidence of GDM is increasing and this has been associated with a number of factors, such as dietary preferences, the changing lifestyles and the age of the mothers (Butt et al. ,2023). One example is the study which revealed a regional trend of rising GDM cases globally, underlined with the main perspective of better depicting risk factors and risk-free strategies (Dellino et al., 2022).

Conclusions

The present study adds essential new findings to existing data on gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) occurrence and extensiveness in pregnant women in Quetta, the capital city of the Balochistan province in Pakistan. The data obtained reveal the fact of the high prevalence of GDM in this community, which stress the necessity of the more focused treatments and better management techniques to reduce the risk of adverse outcomes for both the mother and the fetus. Staging of future investigations will instill work on targeted for specific risk factors, better screening procedures, and all-inclusive diabetes control plans particularized to the context. One of the goals might be to improve the birth outcomes, as well as the long-term health of the mothers and their babies if the increase of demand for maternal health and well-organized care for GDM women is achieved.

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